

Biogeography of freshwater snails (Mollusca: Gastropoda) in various agro-ecological zones across six provinces of South Africa

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INTRODUCTION

- ✓ Freshwater gastropod's role they play as intermediate hosts of trematodes of public health and veterinary important.
- ✓ Their population dynamics and biodiversity are affected by human and animal activities.
- ✓ Climatic and environmental factors, and introduction of invasive snails impact the biodiversity of autochthonous snail populations.
- ✓ These changes often go unnoticed due to poor monitoring and surveillance.

OBJECTIVES

- ✓ To assess the geographic distribution and diversity of freshwater snails in six provinces of South Africa.

METHODOLOGY

Fig 1: Map showing sampling sites.

Fig 2: Sampling site sites.

- 43 water sites were surveyed, and 25 sites had snails
- 3417 snails were collected and identified

RESULTS

- ✓ 13 species from families Lymnaeidae, Planorbidae, Thiaridae, Physidae and Gastrodontidae.

Fig 3: Species distribution and abundance

Fig 4: Habitat preference of freshwater snails

DISCUSSION

- ✓ The highest snail density and species diversity was recorded in the hot semi-arid steppe region of Limpopo province.
- ✓ *Bulinus truncatus* was the only species collected in the cold semi-arid steppe.
- ✓ *Physa acuta* was the most abundant species.
- ✓ *Pseudosuccinea columella* was found in most agro-ecological zones.

CONCLUSION

- ✓ Planorbidae family showed more species diversity.
- ✓ Three invasive snail species were most distributed and utilised diverse habitats.

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